
HOW MOVING COSTS IMPACT SCHELLING'S SEGREGATION MODEL: AN EXTENSION TO THE ORIGINAL MODEL

Hugo Carrasco-Díaz,

Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y de Administración,
Universidad de la República, Uruguay
Montevideo, CP 11200

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-5295-9646>
hugocarrasco66@gmail.com

Cindy Abreo-Álvarez,

Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y de Administración,
Universidad de la República, Uruguay
Montevideo, CP 11200

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-7118-4030>
cindy.abreo@fcea.edu.uy

Ramón Álvarez-Vaz,

Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y de Administración,
Universidad de la República, Uruguay
Montevideo, CP 11200

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2505-4238>
ramon.alvarez@fcea.edu.uy

July 10, 2025

Hugo Carrasco-Díaz: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft;**Cindy Abreo-Álvarez:** Investigation, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft;**Ramón Álvarez-Vaz:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Validation, Visualization, Writing – review & editing;

Declaration of funding sources and conflict of interest The authors declare that they had no external funding source for this research.

Acknowledgments To the entire team of Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y de Administración, Universidad de la República that faithfully collaborated with the investigation. Special thanks to Daniel Ciganda for his collaboration in the implementation of Shiny.

Correspondence Ramón Álvarez-Vaz, E-mail ramon.alvarez@fcea.edu.uy

ABSTRACT

In Schelling's classical model [1], when an individual feels dissatisfied with the number of unwanted "neighbors," they simply move to another free location, but this is restricted by the city's density. Furthermore, it is assumed that in real life, moving has many associated costs. For this reason, it is proposed to modify the model and extend it by considering that each agent starts with a certain amount of monetary units (capital C), and that with each unit of time, each agent manages to save a certain amount of monetary units (savings A). If at any given time they feel dissatisfied and have capital greater than or equal to the cost of moving C_m (moving), then they can move to one of the free locations. Otherwise, they cannot, which means that in the next step they may or may not be dissatisfied, depending on what happened to their neighbors. Using models that consider differential costs by group, different initial capitals, and different savings capacities, the impact of these initial conditions on segregation is studied for certain levels of happiness or satisfaction and intolerance. To carry out the simulation, a graphical interface is programmed in a Shiny application implemented in the statistical language R, making it reproducible and available on an OSF platform server at the following link: <https://osf.io/ngm9h/>.

Keywords Calibration, Agent-based Models, Schelling Model, Monte Carlo Simulation

1 Introduction

Segregation has been a social problem in several countries, and many factors have contributed to it, including zoning laws, housing discrimination (this can include denying certain people the opportunity to live in certain areas or communities because of their race, ethnicity, religion, gender, or other characteristics), among others. Drawing on segregation in 1971, American economist Thomas Schelling [1] developed a model (known as the Schelling Tipping Model) in which he showed that even without explicit intent, people could contribute to segregation through their inadvertent behavior. His segregation model showed that even when individuals (or "agents") did not mind being surrounded by or living next to agents of a different race or economic background, they would still choose to separate from other agents over time and become grouped together according to agent type, [2], [3],[4].

Agents in the model have the ability to move from one plot to another, and this movement is determined by each agent's level of satisfaction with the composition of their neighborhood in each period. Agents are satisfied if the proportion of neighbors in their same group is equal to or greater than a certain tolerance threshold defined a priori. This threshold constitutes the central parameter of the model and is associated with a behavioral rule that, in this case, determines that agents who are not satisfied in one period move randomly to a vacant plot in the following period.

In the classic model, when an individual becomes dissatisfied with the number of unwanted "neighbors," they simply move to another vacant location, but this is subject to restrictions associated with the city's density. Furthermore, it is assumed that in real life, moving entails significant costs. For this reason, it is proposed to continue the work already begun in 2020.[5], to extend the model by adding or modifying some of its parameters. In this case, the variants to the model consist of considering that each agent starts with a certain amount of monetary units (capital C), and that as each unit of time passes, each agent manages to save a certain amount of monetary units (savings). If at any time they feel dissatisfied and have capital greater than or equal to the cost of the move C_m (move), then they can move to one of the free locations. Otherwise, they cannot, which implies that in the next step they may or may not be dissatisfied, depending on what happened to their neighbors.

2 Objectives

The objectives of this work are:

- to assess the impact on segregation when managing different moving costs, and to include other parameters in the original model that have to do with the city's density and the tolerance threshold [6].
- to develop an interactive application through the R language [7], known as *shiny*, that shows the simulation model, where users can manipulate different tabs, in which they can see the evaluation of various segregation-associated metrics and the movement dynamics of agents in the city [8].

The work developed attempts to guarantee the reproducibility postulated in [9],[10], [11], [12], [13].The life cycle of this work consists of a first draft presented in August 2023 with an extended abstract at the *XVI Semana Internacional*

de la Estadística y la Probabilidad, in Facultad de Ciencias Físico Matemáticas de la Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla, México, with the preprint [10.5281/zenodo.13289463](https://zenodo.org/record/13289463). To ensure the reproducibility of the results of the analysis performed, the code and data used are available in a public repository on the OSF platform, which can be accessed at this link <https://osf.io/ngm9h/>.

The document is structured as follows: A methodological development, which appears in section 3.1 and 3.2 on pages 4, then a section with a presentation port the shiny, several results appearing in 4 for some scenarios chosen to show how the expanded model works; finally proposing some conclusions from the findings and possible next steps, which are recorded in section 5 on page 10.

3 Methodology

Two scenarios are considered. In **Scenario 1**, equal initial capital and equal savings per unit of time are assigned to all agents. In **Scenario 2**, inequality is generated between groups by assigning one group a larger initial capital and a greater allocation per period, i.e., a greater savings capacity.

3.1 Scenario 1: Fixed capital, Fixed savings

In the next table we have the different parameters included in the model

Parameter	Description
N	Number of agents
T	Number of plots
$\Psi = \frac{N}{T}$	Density
$p, q = 1 - p$	Percentage of agents in each group
u	Intolerance threshold in both groups
t	Number of iterations
C	Capital for agents in both groups
A	Savings for agents in both groups
v	Moving cost

Table 1: Parameters for Model 1 (without Moving Cost)

In this way, it can be established for this model that there is a function that links the parameters to generate the spatial distribution of the agents.

$$f_1(T, N, p, t, u, C, A) \quad (1)$$

3.2 Scenario 2: Differential Capital, Differential Savings

For **Scenario 2: Model 2 Differential capital, Differential savings** we work with the same parameters as Model 1 with the restriction that $C_1 \geq C_2$ for agents in group 1 with proportion p and $A_1 \geq A_2$ for agents in group 1 with proportion p .

$$f_2(T, N, p, t, u, C_1, C_2, A_1, A_2) \quad (2)$$

For both scenarios, the number of iterations t is predetermined, but each model has a limited duration, either by t or because stability is achieved in the system with $t_e \geq t$. The results are generated using R software, R Core Team (2021), where the computational code developed by Bogumil Kaminski in <https://rsnippets.blogspot.com/2012/04/animating-schellings-segregation-model.html>

Parameter	Description
N	Number of agents
T	Number of plots
$\Psi = \frac{N}{T}$	Density
$p, q = 1 - p$	Percentage of agents in each group
u	Intolerance threshold in both groups
t	Number of iterations
C_1	Capital for agents in group 1
C_2	Capital for agents in group 2
A_1	Savings for agents in group 1
A_2	Savings for agents in group 2
v	Moving cost

Table 2: Parameters for Model 2 (with Moving Cost; variable Capital and Saving)

4 Application using the shiny and some results obtained

In this section of the working paper, we first present a series of screenshots for showing what the shiny application looks like, the different tabs that provide a brief summary, an introduction to the problem, the proposed methodology considering the two models presented above, and a link to a public repository where the shiny application is hosted.

The screenshot shows a web application interface. At the top, there is a horizontal navigation bar with four tabs: "Home", "Introduction", "Evolution of the city", and "Tolerance and similarity matrices". The "Introduction" tab is currently selected. Below the navigation bar, there is a sub-menu with a single tab labeled "Summary". The main content area displays the title "How moving costs impact Schelling's segregation model: An extension to the original model". Below the title, there is a "keywords" section: "Agent-based models - Simulation - Calibration." followed by an "abstract" section. The abstract text reads: "In Schelling's classic model [schelling1971dynamic], when an individual becomes dissatisfied with the number of unwanted 'neighbors,' they simply move to another vacant location. However, this action becomes more complex because it depends on the initial spatial distribution of agents, their number, and the density of the city. On the other hand, it is assumed that in real life, moving has many associated costs. For this reason, it is proposed to modify the model considering that each agent starts with a quantity of monetary units (capital $\backslash(C)$), and that as each unit of time passes each agent manages to save a certain quantity of monetary units (savings $\backslash(A)$), if at any time he feels dissatisfied and has a capital greater than or equal to the cost of the move $\backslash(C_m)$, then he will be able to move to one of the free locations, otherwise he will not be able to do so, which implies that in the next step he may or may not be dissatisfied, depending on what has happened to his neighbors."

Figure 1: Screenshot for shiny application “Initial menu and presentation of a summary of the shiny application” (own elaboration)

Introduction

Segregation has been a social problem in many countries, and many factors have contributed to it, such as zoning laws, housing discrimination (this can include denying certain people the opportunity to live in certain areas or communities because of their race, ethnicity, religion, gender, or other characteristics), among others. Drawing on segregation in 1971, American economist Thomas Schelling developed a model (known as the Schelling Tipping Model) showing that even without explicit intent, people could contribute to segregation through their inadvertent behavior. His segregation model showed that even when individuals (or “agents”) did not mind being surrounded by or living next to agents of a different race or economic background, they would still choose to separate from other agents over time and become clustered based on agent type. [Miller2007], [McCown2013].

Agents in the model have the ability to move from one plot to another, and this movement is determined by each agent’s level of satisfaction with the composition of their neighborhood in each period. Agents are satisfied if the proportion of neighbors from their same group is equal to or greater than a certain tolerance threshold defined a priori. This threshold constitutes the central parameter of the model and is associated with a behavioral rule that, in this case, determines that agents who are not satisfied in one period move to a random empty plot in the following period.

In the classical model, when an individual becomes dissatisfied with the number of unwanted “neighbors,” they simply move to another free location, but this is complicated by the density of our city. Furthermore, it is assumed that in real life, moving has many associated costs. For this reason, it is proposed to modify the model by considering that each agent starts with a certain amount of monetary units (capital $\backslash(C)$), and that with each unit of time, each agent manages to save a certain amount of monetary units (savings $\backslash(A)$). If at any time they feel dissatisfied and have capital greater than or equal to the cost of the move $\backslash(C_m)$, then they can move to one of the free locations; otherwise, they cannot, which implies that in the next step they may or may not be dissatisfied, depending on what has happened to their neighbors.

Figure 2: Screenshot for shiny application “Introduction” (own elaboration)

Methodology

Four scenarios are used. In **Scenario 1**, all agents are assigned equal initial capital and equal savings per unit of time. In **Scenario 2**, inequality is generated between groups by assigning one group a larger initial capital and a larger allocation per period, i.e., savings capacity. In **Scenario 3**, the same parameters as in **Scenario 2** are used, except that the tolerance threshold is considered variable. In **Scenario 4**, the same parameters are used as in Scenario 2, except that population density is considered variable.

Scenario 1:

- Number of agents $\backslash(N)$
- Number of parcels $\backslash(T)$
- Density $\backslash(\Psi = \frac{N}{T})$
- Percentage of agents out of the total that belong to one of the groups $\backslash(p)$ and $\backslash(q = 1 - p)$ in the remaining group
- The intolerance threshold $\backslash(u)$ is the same in both groups
- Number of iterations $\backslash(t)$
- Capital $\backslash(C)$ for agents in both groups
- Savings $\backslash(A)$ for agents in both groups
- Move cost $\backslash(\epsilon) = 0$

Scenario 2: Inequality between groups, by assigning one group a higher initial capital and greater savings capacity (Differential Capital, Differential Savings).

Scenario 3 The same parameters as above are used, except that the tolerance threshold will be considered variable. The tolerance threshold varies from 0 to 1 ($u = 0$ to 1).

Scenario 4 The same parameters as above are used, except that the population density will be considered variable. The population density varies from 0.45 to 0.95 ($\Psi = 0.45$ to 0.95).

Figure 3: Screenshot for shiny application “Methodology used in the shiny” (own elaboration)

Reproducibility

To ensure the reproducibility of the results of the analysis, the code and data used were made available in a public repository, which can be accessed through this link: <https://gitlab.com/meda3/extensions-to-the-schelling-segregation-model-inclusion-of-moving-costs>

Conclusions

The first general conclusion reached is that moving costs influence the model, generating a postponement of moves, with an increase in the level of dissatisfaction among agents, and a lag in segregation levels. For societies with medium levels of acceptance, high levels of dissatisfaction are not generated, but if the time is prolonged, high levels of similarity (i.e., high levels of segregation) would be reached. In the case of differential moving costs, it can be seen that although one group has greater economic power than the other, if the value of the move remains constant for all agents, it is found that, ultimately, behavior as a society ends up being "average," thus favoring the "less well-off." This situation is due to the fact that, for moderate moving cost values, achieving greater similarity among those in group 2 (the richest) results in greater similarity among many in group 1.

At the beginning of this work, the question arose as to what the new intra- and inter-group dynamics would be like. The answer is that the economic differences between groups converge to an average behavior, leading to slightly similar final results.

As a future work, the goal is to empirically evaluate the change in the models' input parameters, considering some appropriate probability distributions by randomizing some of the components, such as income, moving costs, density, tolerance, and a possible feedback loop in the system between some of the components that could function as incentives or perhaps allow agents to receive a subsidy, for example, for the cost of moving.

Figure 4: Screenshot for shiny application "Conclusions for the differents models simulated" (own elaboration)

4.1 Results for model 1

Then we present some results that arise from studying the behavior of agents under *Model 1*, in terms of their similarity proportions between agents who live in the same neighborhoods and the level of unhappiness they feel having neighbors from the other group. The work is implemented in [7] and uses libraries [8],[14]. For this purpose, and as a first approximation, for the case of *Model 1*, for a fixed density level $\psi = 0.6$ and a fixed preference level $u = 0.6$, the behavior when the cost of moving ν is zero (classical model)

The number of plots is $T = 2061$, Density $\Psi = 0.6$, the percentage of agents from group 1 $p = 0.5$ and $q = 0.5$ in the remaining group, the intolerance threshold $u = 0.6$ equal in both groups, The number of iterations $t = 50$, Capital $C_1 = 4$ for group 1 and $C_2 = 4$ for group 2, Savings $A_1 = 2$ and $A_2 = 2$ and Moving cost $\nu = 0$.

Chart of the city at the end of the time period

Figure 5: Simulation: Density $\psi = 0.6$, Preference $u = 0.6$, Moving $\nu = 0$.

It can be observed how the growth of the proportion of similarity and the decrease of the proportion of unhappy people are characterized by being 'smooth' functions, the first increasing and the second decreasing.

Figure 6: Density $\psi = 0.6$, Preference $u = 0.6$, Moving $\nu = 0$.

4.2 Results for model 2

For the *Model 2* we have those values for parameters: The number of plots $T = 2061$, Density $\Psi = 0.8$, the percentage of agents from group 1 $p = 0.5$ and $q = 0.5$ in the remaining group, the intolerance threshold $u = 0.6$ equal in both groups, the number of iterations $t = 50$, Capital $C_1 = 4$ and $C_2 = 10$, Savings $A_1 = 1$ and $A_2 = 2$ and Moving cost are $\nu = c(2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12)$.

You can see through the shiny how the metrics are displayed with high-level graphics that are also interactive through the use of the *plotly* [14] functions.

When the cost of moving C is incorporated, behaviors begin that demonstrate postponing the time of moving. When the cost of moving is 2, small disturbances appear in the similarity and unhappiness lines, but at values 4 and higher, "steps" begin to appear, becoming more frequent and longer as the cost of moving C increases. Clearly, total happiness levels are not reached over 50-year horizons, since evaluating moving behavior consists not only of detecting the level of dissatisfaction, but also of two relevant magnitudes that determine the "capital" that must be sufficient and the passage of time.

Figure 7: Density $\psi = 0.6$, Preference $u = 0.6$, Moving $\nu = c(2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12)$.

One aspect that is also being worked on is a visualization to see at what point the metrics of similar and dissatisfied people become equal, as shown in Figure 8a, which analytically can be seen as a problem of roots of non-linear equations.

If we now analyze what happens for fixed preferences (0.6) and varying the density from 45% to 95%, for different values of the move, and for the fixed density (0.7) and varying the preference from 0% to 100%, for different values of the move, it is shown in Figures 8a and 8b.

(a) Relationship between variable tolerance threshold and fixed density.

(b) Relationship between fixed tolerance threshold and variable density.

Figure 8: Relationships between u and Ψ for different moving costs, c setting Capital $C_1 = 4$ and $C_2 = 10$ and Savings $A_1 = 1$ and $A_2 = 2$.

5 Conclusions and future steps

The first general conclusion reached is that moving costs influence the model, generating a postponement of moves, with an increase in the level of dissatisfaction on the part of agents, and a lag in segregation levels. For societies with medium levels of acceptance, high levels of dissatisfaction are not generated, but if the time is prolonged, high levels of similarity (i.e., high levels of segregation) would be reached. In the case of inequality, it can be seen that although one group has greater economic power than the other, when the value of the move remains constant for all agents, it is found that, ultimately, behavior as a society ends up being "average," thus favoring the "less well-off." This situation is due to the fact that for moderate values of moving costs, achieving greater similarity among those in group 2 (the richest) results in greater similarity among many in group 1.

At the beginning of this work, the question arose as to what the new intra- and inter-group dynamics would be like, and the answer is that the economic differences between the groups converge to an average behavior, reaching slightly similar final results.

An interesting aspect is that it is possible to have a user-friendly product, implemented in the R language, which is today the paradigmatic computational tool in the field of applied statistics and which complements the developments made in other tools such as *Netlogo* [15] or *Cormas* [16], which are specifically designed to analyze agent-based models and which have specific modules for Schelling models. An advantage of doing it entirely in the R language is that it is easier to extend the analysis to be able to work with the different metrics, adding aspects of statistical learning and numerical methods, to find analytical expressions of the curves that follow the different metrics and their cut-off point.

As future plans remain to be made

References

- [1] Schelling, Thomas C. *Dynamic models of segregation*. Journal of Mathematical Sociology, 1971. Vol. 1, No. 2, pp. 143–186. Publisher: Taylor & Francis.
- [2] Miller, John and Page, Scott. *Complex Adaptive Systems: An Introduction to Computational Models of Social Life*. 2007. ISBN: 9780691127026. URL: <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691127026/complex-adaptive-systems>.
- [3] McCown, Frank. *Schelling's Model of Segregation*. May 2023. Available at: <http://nifty.stanford.edu/2014/mccown-schelling-model-segregation/>.
- [4] Urrutia-Mosquera, J., López-Ospina, H., Sabatini, F., y Rasse, A. (2017). *Tolerancia a la diversidad y segregación residencial. Una adaptación del modelo de segregación de Schelling con tres grupos sociales*. EURE (Santiago), 43:5 – 24.
- [5] De Armas, G, Rodriguez-Collazo, S, Álvarez-Vaz, R, Carrasco,H y Ciganda, D. (2020). *Extensiones al modelo de segregación de Schelling, primera parte. (Serie Documentos de Trabajo;2/20)*. Universidad de la República (Uruguay). Facultad de Ciencias Económicas y de Administración. Instituto de Estadística,https://iesta.fcea.udelar.edu.uy/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/ddt_02_20.pdf
- [6] Murdoch, Duncan and Adler, Daniel. *rgl: 3D Visualization Using OpenGL*. 2022. R package version 0.109.6. URL: <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=rgl>.
- [7] R Core Team (2024). *R: A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing*,url = <https://www.R-project.org/>
- [8] Chang, Winston et al. *shiny: Web Application Framework for R*. 2023. R package version 1.7.4.9002. URL: <https://shiny.rstudio.com/>.
- [9] Peng, R. D. 2009 . Reproducible research and Biostatistics, *Biostatistics* **10**(3): 405–408. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biostatistics/kxp014>
- [10] Gandrud, C. 2015 n.d. . *Reproducible Research with R and R Studio*.
- [11] Gandrud, C., 2019 Reproducible research with r and rstudio. <https://github.com/christophergandrud/Rep-Res-Book>
- [12] Glennie, R. , 2021 Reproducible research with r and rstudio (3rd edition) by christopher gandrud, *Journal of Agricultural, Biological and Environmental Statistics* **26**(1): 128–129. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13253-020-00418-y>
- [13] Kohrs, F. E.and Auer, S., Bannach-Brown, A., Fiedler, S., Haven, T. L., Heise, V. Weissgerber, T. L. 2023 . Eleven strategies for making reproducible research and open science training the norm at research institutions., *techreport*.
- [14] Sievert, C. *Interactive Web-Based Data Visualization with R, plotly and shiny*.Chapman and Hall/CRC Florida, 2020.
- [15] Wilensky, U. (1999). *NetLogo*. <http://ccl.northwestern.edu/netlogo/>. Center for Connected Learning and Computer-Based Modeling, Northwestern University, Evanston, IL.
- [16] Zaitsev, O. and Vendel F. and Delay E. ,(2023) *Cormas: The Software for Participatory Modelling and its Application for Managing Natural Resources in Senegal*, <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.12534>